

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

In the second regular issue of volume 18 we have five accepted papers. Not only is the variety of topics worth mentioning, but also the authors' geographical location dispersed over five countries and even three continents. Allow me to thank the members of our editorial board for their support in reviewing the articles. Naturally, I'd also like to thank the many members of our editorial board who reviewed articles which did not make it to publication.

In this issue, Grzegorz Chmaj and Krzysztof Walkowiak from Poland cover distributed computing research by investigating and discussing delivering methods for efficient download of items by numerous users. Ismael Hasan, Javier Parapar and Alvaro Barreiro from Spain focus on text processing in their research on a new method for text extraction in PDFs of complex text formats by simulation human reading order. Jong Wook Kim, Ashwin Kashyap and Sandilya Bhamidipati from USA contribute with a paper on their research in natural language processing and semantics by an efficient and effective algorithm using Wikipedia as semantic interpreter. The authors Ahmed Nait-Sidi-Moh, Mohamed Bakhouya, Wafaa Ait-Cheik-Bihi and Jaafar Gaber from France and Finland deal with important security research by discussing the purpose and the usage of digital signature on negotiated electronic queries between a server and clients in service discovery systems and web service composition. Finally, Mabel Vazquez-Briseno, Pierre Vincent, Juan Ivan Nieto-Hipolito and Juan de Dios Sanchez-Lope from Mexico focus on mobile computing aspects by a new framework for generating mobile applications and services.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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